

SINGLE LINE CASE STUDY ON SHEETAPITTA (Urticaria)**DR ADITYA TURANKAR****DR RASHMI KADU****Associate Professor, Panchakarma Department, Shri.K.R.Pandav Ayurved college
Nagpur****Associate Professor Kaumarbhritya Department Gurukunj Ashram, Dist Amravati****INTRODUCTION**

In *Ayurveda*, *Sheetapitta* is mentioned as one of the *Twak Vikara*. *Sheetapitta* is composed of two words, *Sheeta* and *Pitta*, which are contrary to each other in meaning. The word *Sheeta* indicates *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha* and their association with *Pitta Dosha*. According to *Madhav Nidana*, *Sheetapitta* is caused by exposure to a cold breeze, which results in the vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha*, predominantly in association with *Pitta Dosha*. Due to the impairment of *Doshas*, it leads to *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu Dushti*, then spreads towards the extremities and manifests as maculopapular rash. *Sheetapitta*, *Udarda*, and *Kotha* are three different terminologies mentioned in *Samhita*, having a few different characteristics and different causative factors. The specific reference for *Sheetapitta* is not found in *Brihtrayee*, but these terms are mentioned as *Purvarupa Lakshana* and *Vyadhi*. *Madhukosa* explained that, though the features of *Sheetapitta* and *Udarda* are similar to each other, there is a predominance of *Vata Dosha* in *Sheetapitta* while *Udarda* is dominated by *Kapha Dosha*. The etiological factors responsible for *Sheetapitta* appear due to the consumption of *Asatmya Ahar* or various kinds of allergens. In today's advanced lifestyle, improper and unhealthy food habits lead to lower nutritional value in the diet, resulting in *Dhatu Daurbalya* and impaired immune responses. This causes sensitization towards allergens and produces allergic reactions. *Sheetapitta* can be correlated with urticaria due to the resemblance of etiological factors and symptomatology. Urticaria affects about 20% of the population at some point in their lifetime.

If it continues for more than 6 weeks, then it is said to be chronic urticaria. Upto 45% of the patients with chronic urticaria have an autoimmune cause for their disease. The present study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of *Shaman Chikitsa* in *Sheetapitta*.

Aim and Objectives

To study *Sheetapitta Vyadhi* (Urticaria) and to assess the competency of *Shaman Chikitsa* in *Sheetapitta Vyadhi*.

Case Report

A 54-year-old male patient with a medium build reported to the OPD and presented with chief complaints of elevated reddish irregular lesions with swelling. The above complaints have been

associated with the gradual onset of itching and burning sensations all over the body for 8 months. Itching starts immediately after the consumption of food items like spices, citrus fruits, oily food, dry fruits, and nuts. The symptoms are aggravated more at night and at winter season (cold touch), and gradually subside in the morning. The diagnosis was done as *Sheetapitta* on the basis of etiological factors and clinical presentation.

History

The patient had no history of any systemic disease, no medical or surgical history.

Personal history

Occupation – bus driver

Nidana

Due to *Sheeta Marutadi Sevan* (exposure to cold wind and cold weather), *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha* get vitiated and mixed with *Pitta Dosha*. All three vitiated *Doshas* spread all over the body and manifests as *Sheetapitta*

1. *Aharaj Hetu - Atiamla Sevan, Atilavan, Atikatu Sevan, Kshara Sevan, Viruddha Ahar Sevan, Dadhi Sevan.*
2. *Viharaj Hetu - Sheet Maruta Sevan, Bahya Krumi, Keeta Damsga, Chardi Nigrahan, Shishir Ritu, Vastra, Abhushan.*
3. *Nidanaarthakara Roga - Pittaja and Kaphaja Jwara, Sannipatika Roga, Unmarda, Adhoga Amlapitta.*

Poorvarup (Premonitory signs)

Pipasa (Thirst), *Aruchi* (loss of appetite), *Hrillasa* (Nausea), *Dehasaad* (Feeling of tiredness), *Anga Gaurava* (Feeling of heaviness), *Rakta Lochanata* (Redness of eyes).

Rupa (Signs and Symptoms)

Varti Damshta Samsthana Shotha (Inflammation like an insect bite), *Kandu Bahula* (Severe itching), *Toda Bahula* (Excessive pain like pricking), *Chardi* (Vomiting), *Jvara* (Fever), *Vidaha* (Burning Sensation), *Ksanikotpatti Vinasha*.

Samprapti Ghataka

Dosha: Tridosha

Agni: Mandagni

Vyadhimarga: Bahya

Dushya: Rasa, Rakta

Srotas: Rasavaha, Raktavaha

Srotodushtiprakara: VimargaGamana

\UdbhavaSthana: Aamashaya

VyaktiSthana: Tvak

Svabhava: Ashukari

General Examination

Pulse: 82/min

B.P: 110/80 mmHg

RR: 18/min

Temp: 98.2°F

Weight: 70Kg

Height: 5.2”

Appetite: anorexia

Sleep: disturbed

CHIKITSA –

It can be divided into three phases, i.e.

1) Shodhan

2)Shaman

3)Pathya– Apathya

In Charak Vimansthan, it is stated that

- Bahu Doshavastha-Shodhan
- Madhya Doshavastha-Langhan, Pachani, e. Shaman
- Hina Doshavastha–Langhan

SHODHAN CHIKITSA

A) Vamana: Vamana by Patola, Nimba, and Vasa Kwatha is said to be useful as a treatment for Sheetpitta.

B) Virechana: Virechana is performed by Triphala, Guggulu, and Pippali, which is best for treating Sheepitta, or by Nishoth+Gandharv Haritaki.

C) Raktamokshan: After Abhyantar Snehan with Mahatikta Ghrita, Raktamokshan is useful in the treatment of Sheetpitta.

Abhayantar

Haridra Khanda with water, bd after a meal

Bilwadi Gutika 500mg with water bd

Avipattikar Churna- 10 gm with lukewarm water hs

Maricha has

Assessment Criteria

Assessment of the patient was done on the basis of improvement in subjective parameters like *Kotha* (inflammation), *Kandu* (itching), and *Daha* (burning sensation).

Observation

Symptoms	Observed	Score
Kotha (Raised edematous wheals of pink-red colour)	3	1
Kandu (itching)	2	1
Toda (pricking sensation)	2	0
Daha (burning sensation)	3	0

Discussion

Before treatment, assessment and examination of the patient were done on the basis of Urticaria Activity Score (UAS). The diagnosis was that the patient was suffering from a grade 3 urticarial phase. After a month of taking continuous treatment, the grading of Urticaria Activity Score (UAS) and clinical features of a patient were reduced significantly. Remarkable changes were

evident after 2 months of treatment with the above-mentioned medicine. This single case report concludes that Ayurvedic management with *Shaman Chikitsa* offers excellent results in the treatment of *Sheetapitta*.

Haridra Khanda¹- *Haridra Khanda* is the drug of choice for *Sheetapitta* mentioned by *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*. It is a potent anti-allergic drug; it has anti-bacterial and anti-microbial properties.

Dushivishari Agada - Most of the ingredients possess *Katu*, *Tikta*, *Rasatmaka*, and *Katu Rasa* properties, which are *Krumihar*, *Kushthar*, and *Vishaghna* properties. It clears *Kapha* and *Kleda* from *Strotas*.

Bilwadi Gutika - Majority of the drugs of *Bilwadi Agad* are *Tikta*, *Katu Rasa Pradhan*, and are *Ushna Veerya* (hot potency) and *Katu Vipaki*; thus, can act as *Vishaghna* and *Keetaghna*.

Avipattikar Churna- It causes *Raktaprasadana* by eliminating *Dushta Kapha*, *Pitta Dosha*, and *Kleda* from *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu*.

Maricha - *Maricha* contains an active principle called piperine, because of which it has an anti-inflammatory effect. *Ayurveda* has a considerable amount of potential in the treatment aspect of allergic skin diseases by using various formulations, followed by *Pathya-Apathya*.

PATHYAAPATHYA:

Pathya-Apathya plays an important role in the management of any disease. *Pathya* is that which is suitable to the disease and to the diseased. (Things to do). While *Apathya* is unsuitable, it aggravates the disease process, leading to more discomfort for the patients. (Things not to do). *Pathya* and *Apathya* for *Sheetpitta* are as follows:

Pathya – *Jeerna Shali*, *Mudga Yusha*, *Shigru Shaka*, *Patola Shaka*, *Triphala*, *Ushnodaka*, *Jangala Mamsa*, *Kulatha Yusha*, *Karvellaka Shaka*, *Dadima Phala*, *Madhu*, *Katu*, *Tikta*, *Kashaya Rasa*, *Lava-tilkta Mamsa Rasa*.

Apathya – *Matsaya*, *Poorva*, and *Dakshin Disha Pavana*, *Naveena Madya*, *Chhardi Nigraha*, *Divaswapna*, *Snana*, *Virudhaahara*, *Aatap Sevana*, *Vyavaaya*, *Snigdha*, *Amla*, *Madhura Dravya*, *Guru Annapana*.

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